

Distribution and genetic diversity of the invasive clinging jellyfish *Gonionemus vertens* on Nantucket and Muskeget Islands

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Abstract

The goals of this project were to document the distribution of the invasive clinging jellyfish *Gonionemus* in Nantucket and Muskeget Islands and to analyze its regional population genetic diversity. *Gonionemus* is native to the north Pacific coasts and was first documented locally in Woods Hole and Muskeget Island in the early 20th century. This form of *Gonionemus* was not associated with painful stings, despite frequent handling by scientists and collectors. An invasion of a more toxic form of *Gonionemus* appears to have occurred in the late 1980s in the Cape Cod region. Several individuals have reported *Gonionemus* stings in parts of Waquoit Bay (Cape Cod) and Martha's Vineyard, but none to date have been recorded from Nantucket. Jellyfish surveys were coordinated with Mary Carman (WHOI) who conducted a parallel NBI study on the distribution and abundance of invasive tunicates in eelgrass meadows on Nantucket and Muskeget Islands. Despite extensive searching, no *Gonionemus* were found on either Nantucket or Muskeget. However, a broader genetic analysis of regional *Gonionemus* populations indicated the presence of multiple lineages, one of which is shared with well-known toxic populations in the Sea of Japan. The unique lineages indicated that native *Gonionemus* diversity also likely exists in the area. While no *Gonionemus* were found on Nantucket or Muskeget, it is possible that *Gonionemus* may arrive in the near future. The life cycle of *Gonionemus* includes minute asexual stages which could easily hitchhike on ship hulls and other vectors. Monitoring eelgrass habitats will facilitate early detection, so that mitigation measures can be most effectively applied.

Introduction

The clinging jellyfish *Gonionemus* (Cnidaria, Hydrozoa, Limnomedusae; Fig. 1A) is thought to be an invasive species on Cape Cod and elsewhere (Govindarajan and Carman, 2016). *Gonionemus vertens* was first described from Puget Sound on the North American Pacific coast

(Agassiz, 1862), and is found in other parts of the North Pacific, especially on the Alaskan, Russian, Chinese, and Japanese coasts (Yakovlev and Vaskovsky, 1993). *Gonionemus* is invasive in Europe along the Mediterranean, North Atlantic, and North Sea coasts (Tambis-Lyche, 1964; Bakker, 1980), in the Cape Cod, Massachusetts region, and in Argentina (Rodriguez et al., 2014). In the Cape Cod region, *Gonionemus* was first recorded as *Gonionemus murbachii* in Eel Pond in Woods Hole and on Muskeget Island (Gordon, 1915), although it was later considered to be a form of *G. vertens* (Naumov, 1960).

Unlike most jellyfish which are pelagic, *Gonionemus* medusae are strongly associated with seagrass and macroalgal beds (Bakker, 1980). In Cape Cod, medusae appear to be primarily associated with the eelgrass *Zostera marina* (Fig. 1B). Medusae cling to the seagrasses and algae using the adhesive pads on their tentacles. Their activity appears to be related to both time of day and weather conditions (Edwards, 1976). During calm, sunny daylight hours, the medusae cling to the seagrasses and algae. During evenings and when the sky is overcast, medusae are more commonly found swimming out of the eelgrass towards the surface, where they flip over and sink with their tentacles extended to catch zooplankton. Mature jellyfish range in size from 1 to 3 cm.

Some *Gonionemus* medusae can cause severe pain and neurological and neuropsychiatric symptoms comparable to Irukandji (box jellyfish) syndrome (Gershwin et al., 2003). Symptoms include burning, edema, numbness, difficult respiration, severe pain, and liver problems (Yakovlev and Vaskovsky, 1993) and may persist 3 – 5 days. Until 1990, severe stings were only known from Northwest Pacific populations from the Sea of Japan (Naumov, 1960; Yakovlev and Vaskovsky, 1993). Eastern Pacific and North Atlantic forms, including the Cape and Islands – area and European forms, were reported to be non-toxic to humans. However, coincident with the increase in the Cape Cod and Martha’s Vineyard-area sightings since 1990, there has been several reports of several severe stings similar to those from the western Pacific. The frequency of severe stings, as well as new *Gonionemus* sightings, appears to be increasing (Govindarajan and Carman, 2016). These observations suggest a new invasion of the more toxic western Pacific form of *G. vertens*. The goals of this project were to 1) document the distribution of *Gonionemus* on Nantucket and Muskeget; and 2) as part of a broader effort, analyze regional population genetic diversity in order to better understand the origin and invasion history of Northwest Atlantic *Gonionemus*.

Methods

Jellyfish surveys - Sampling on Nantucket and Muskeget was coordinated with Carman's NBI tunicate surveys, as tunicates co-occur with *Gonionemus* in eelgrass meadows (Fig. 1B).

Logistical assistance was provided by the Nantucket Conservation Foundation and the Maria Mitchell Association. Eelgrass meadows were accessed from shore or with a small boat. Jellyfish were searched for by running nets through the eelgrass (Fig. 2), a method that has been successful in other *Gonionemus* surveys. Only nets provided by the Maria Mitchell Association were used in order to avoid any chance of contaminating Nantucket habitats with non-indigenous organisms.

Genetic diversity – The mitochondrial COI gene from *Gonionemus* medusae obtained from regional and possible Pacific source populations was sequenced as part of a larger effort (supported by the Woods Hole Sea Grant) on determining the origin and invasion history of Northwest Atlantic *Gonionemus*. DNA was extracted, and the COI gene was amplified using primers described by Folmer et al. (1994) and standard PCR conditions and protocols (e.g., Govindarajan et al., 2015). Purified DNA was sequenced in both directions at MWG Eurofins Operon. DNA sequences were aligned and analyzed using the Geneious software platform (Biomatters). As well, a subset of *Gonionemus* DNA extractions are being used to obtain single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) data using Restriction site-Associated DNA (RAD) sequencing (Davey et al., 2011), conducted at Floragenex (<http://www.floragenex.com/>).

Results

No *Gonionemus* jellyfish were found in any of the surveys conducted by Govindarajan and Carman on Nantucket or Muskeget (Table 1). In an analysis of genetic diversity, three mitochondrial COI lineages were found in Northwest Atlantic *Gonionemus* populations. One of these lineages was identical to that found in highly toxic *Gonionemus* populations in the Sea of Japan, while the other two lineages were unique, suggesting that both introduced and native forms may be present in this region. Also, Northwest Atlantic and Northwest Pacific sequences differed substantially from Northeast Pacific and

Northeast Atlantic *Gonionemus* sequences, suggesting that these forms may actually represent different species. The COI results have been submitted for publication:

Govindarajan AF, Carman MR, Khaidarov M, Semenchenco A, Wares JP. Submitted. Refining a zoogeographic puzzle: Mitochondrial diversity in the clinging jellyfish *Gonionemus* and its implications for understanding the origins of clinging jellyfish in the Northwest Atlantic.

A copy of the paper will be provided to Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) upon publication. As well, any future publications that were supported by NBI funds (e.g., the results of the anticipated single nucleotide polymorphism dataset, which is not yet analyzed) will also be provided to NBI.

Discussion

As *Gonionemus* was not found in any of the surveys, it seems unlikely that Nantucket or Muskeget currently has an active *Gonionemus* population. In the Woods Hole area, *Gonionemus* nearly disappeared in 1930 due to a regional dieoff of eelgrass, *Gonionemus*'s preferred substrate. It is possible that any Nantucket or Muskeget populations died off at that time as well. However, as *Gonionemus* is making a resurgence in Cape Cod and Martha's Vineyard, Nantucket may be at risk for receiving a new influx, potentially of the highly toxic form. *Gonionemus* has a complex life cycle that includes minute polyp and cyst stages (Perkins, 1902; Uchida, 1976) that would easily go undetected on ship hulls or other vectors. Thus, it is possible that *Gonionemus* may become established on Nantucket in the near future. Awareness and early detection could help with prevention and/or mitigation strategies which would be most effective in the early stage of an invasion.

As no *Gonionemus* was found in our surveys, I could not include Nantucket or Muskeget samples in the genetic analysis. However, the COI results from the broader genetic study effort showed that New England coastal areas contain at least three lineages, one of which is shared with highly toxic Sea of Japan populations. It is possible that the other two lineages could represent native *Gonionemus* diversity. Many marine invertebrates have cryptic population histories due to unresolved taxonomy and poor

historical documentation. Additional genetic studies using single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) will help to disentangle *Gonionemus*'s complex Northwest Atlantic history and shed light on its recent resurgence.

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Table 1. Survey areas on Nantucket, including those conducted by Annette Govindarajan and Mary Carman.

Site name	Latitude	Longitude
Nantucket Harbor	N41° 16.936'	W70° 05.653'
Brant Point Shellfish Hatchery	N41° 17.341'	W70° 05.459'
Town Dock	N41° 16.913'	W70° 05.569'
Madaket Harbor	N41° 16.567'	W70° 11.724'
Madaket Marine	N41° 16.755'	W70° 11.525'
Walter S. Barrett Public Pier	N41° 16.486'	W70° 11.831'
Polpis Harbor	N41 ° 18.140'	W70 ° 01.120'
Jackson Point	N41° 16.291'	W70° 12.071'

Figure 1. A) *Gonionemus* medusae collected from Waquoit Bay. B) The blue arrow points to a cryptic medusa clinging to an eelgrass blade. The eelgrass blade is also fouled with invasive tunicates.

Figure 2. Searching for jellyfish using nets. Photos courtesy of Andrew McKenna-Foster.

